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“EXTRA JUDICIAL KILLINGS: BEFORE AND BEYOND 2016”

As cold as the night is,
I have a lot of questions again.

What? Why? Where? When? Who? How?
Questions that a book cannot answer.

How many thousands more innocent people will be hurt?
If it is a war on drugs, go ahead!

How many thousands more will die?
We screamed silently, just "Ahay!" so loudly.

I don't see anything wrong,
If the news is about the war on drugs.

However, if someone innocent is hurt,
I am always willing to take this single voice to bigger crowd.

Enough! Too much! Out of place already!
Because there are so many innocent victims.

The night is as cold as,
Justice not served!